

Supplementary Material for the Publication “Innovation by Information Technology Recombination: How Artificial Intelligence Progressive Web Apps Foster Sustainable Development”

Philipp Fukas ¹, Oliver Thomas

Introduction

The following ten online databases were searched:

- ACM Digital Library (<https://dl.acm.org/>)
- AIS Electronic Library (<https://aisel.aisnet.org/>)
- EBSCO Host (<https://search.ebscohost.com>)
- Emerald Insight (<https://www.emerald.com/insight/>)
- Google Scholar (<https://scholar.google.de/>)
- IEEE Xplore (<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/Xplore/home.jsp>)
- Science Direct (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/>)
- Springer Link (<https://link.springer.com/>)
- Web of Science (<https://webofscience.com/>)
- Wiley Online Library (<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/>)

The following search strings were used and the results were combined:

(“Artificial Intelligence” OR “Computational Intelligence” OR “Machine Intelligence” OR “Cognitive Computing”) AND “Progressive Web App”

(“Data-driven” OR “Data Science” OR “Big Data” OR “Data Analytics”) AND “Progressive Web App”

(“Computer Vision” OR “Natural Language Processing” OR “Machine Learning” OR “Deep Learning” OR “Robotics” OR “Knowledge Representation” OR “Expert Systems”) AND “Progressive Web App”

Finally, the search yielded in 62 relevant publications. These publications were analysed towards their technical components as well as their sustainability and managerial impacts using a concept matrix approach.

¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2169-5505>

Source	Computer Vision	Deduction, Reasoning, Problem Solving	Knowledge Representation	Machine Learning	Natural Language Processing	Planning	Robotics	Social Intelligence
[Ac20]				X	X			
[Ai18]								X
[Al17]				X				
[Ap20]			X	X	X			
[Be20]				X	X			
[Bi19]	X			X				
[BK21]	X			X	X	X		
[Br20]	X			X				
[BTN20]			X					
[Ca19]			X					
[Ce21]				X				
[Ch20]				X				
[Ci20]	X							
[Da21]						X	X	
[De20]				X		X		
[Di18]	X			X				
[Ea19]				X		X		
[EKK19]		X	X	X				
[Ga19]				X				X
[Gr20]		X	X	X				
[HS20]				X	X			
[HB19]					X			

Source	Computer Vision	Deduction, Reasoning, Problem Solving	Knowledge Representation	Machine Learning	Natural Language Processing	Planning	Robotics	Social Intelligence
[HZ18]			X					
[Hu19]	X			X				
[Ka20]				X	X			
[Kh17]		X	X					
[Ku20]			X					
[La18]				X		X		
[Li20]	X							
[LR19]			X					
[LSK20]					X			
[Ly18]				X	X			
[Ma20a]	X							
[Ma18]						X	X	
[Ma20b]		X	X			X		
[Mc20]				X				
[Me19]				X				
[MB20]			X	X				
[Mu20]					X	X		
[NLA19]				X		X		
[Ou19]				X				
[Pa17]					X			
[PNB19]					X			

Source	Computer Vision	Deduction, Reasoning, Problem Solving	Knowledge Representation	Machine Learning	Natural Language Processing	Planning	Robotics	Social Intelligence
[PSM20a]	X							
[PSM20b]	X							
[Ri20]				X				
[Rw18]					X			
[Sa21]				X				
[Sa19a]		X	X					
[Sa19b]		X	X					
[Sh20]				X				
[Sp19]				X				X
[SRW20]	X							
[Sz19]				X		X		
[Tu18]				X				
[Va20]				X				
[Vi17]	X			X				
[VGG20]				X		X		
[We19]	X				X			
[Wi19]	X			X				
[YY19]				X				
[Zh20]	X							
Sum	15	6	13	36	14	11	2	3

Tab. 1: Artificial Intelligence Component Concept Matrix

Source	Process Efficiency	Cost Efficiency	Consumption Optimisation	Usage Optimisation	Enabled Society	Engaged Society
[Ac20]					X	
[Ai18]						X
[Al17]			X			
[Ap20]					X	
[Be20]						X
[Bi19]		X				
[BK21]	X					
[Br20]						X
[BTN20]	X					
[Ca19]						X
[Ce21]						X
[Ch20]			X			
[Ci20]				X	X	
[Da21]				X		
[De20]					X	
[Di18]					X	
[Ea19]				X		
[EKK19]	X					
[Ga19]						X
[Gr20]					X	
[HS20]					X	
[HB19]						X

Source	Process Efficiency	Cost Efficiency	Consumption Optimisation	Usage Optimisation	Enabled Society	Engaged Society
[HZ18]				X		
[Hu19]					X	
[Ka20]					X	
[Kh17]						X
[Ku20]	X					
[La18]				X		
[Li20]					X	
[LR19]						
[LSK20]				X		
[Ly18]					X	
[Ma20a]				X	X	
[Ma18]				X		
[Ma20b]						
[Mc20]						X
[Me19]		X				
[MB20]	X					
[Mu20]					X	
[NLA19]	X					
[Ou19]				X	X	
[Pa17]						X
[PNB19]					X	
[PSM20a]	X					

Source	Process Efficiency	Cost Efficiency	Consumption Optimisation	Usage Optimisation	Enabled Society	Engaged Society
[PSM20b]	X					
[Ri20]						X
[Rw18]					X	
[Sa21]						X
[Sa19a]						X
[Sa19b]						X
[Sh20]						X
[Sp19]						X
[SRW20]					X	
[Sz19]	X					
[Tu18]	X					
[Va20]					X	
[Vi17]	X					
[VGG20]			X			
[We19]					X	
[Wi19]					X	
[YY19]						X
[Zh20]						
Sum	11	2	3	9	20	17

Tab. 2: Sustainability Concept Matrix

Bibliography

- [Ac20] Accame, D. et al.: Adapting client application of feature phone based on experiment parameters, U.S. Patent Pub. No. US20200364067A1, 2020.
- [Ai18] Aikaterini, T.: Affective system monitoring personal expenses, helping the user to stay on budget, International Hellenic University, 2018.
- [Al17] Alurkar, A. A. et al.: A Proposed Data Science Approach for Email Spam Classification using Machine Learning Techniques. *Internet of Things Business Models, Users, and Networks*, pp. 1–5, 2017.
- [Ap20] Apolinario-Arzube, Ó. et al.: CollaborativeHealth: Smart Technologies to Surveil Outbreaks of Infectious Diseases Through Direct and Indirect Citizen Participation. *Applied Informatics and Cybernetics in Intelligent Systems*, pp. 177–190, 2020.
- [Be20] Bergkvist, A. et al. : Sumrize: An Online NLP System for and Summarization, Uppsala University, 2020.
- [Bi19] Bilsten, J.: Generating a website from digital image metadata, U.S. Patent Pub. No. US20190065613A1, 2019.
- [BK21] Bhola, T.; Kaul, S.: SMART EV: Dynamic Pricing and Waiting Period Prediction at EV Charging Station. In (Deepak, G. et al., eds.): *International Conference on Innovative Computing and Communications*, pp. 725–735, 2021.
- [Br20] Briese, C. et al.: Towards Deep Learning in Industrial Applications Taking Advantage of Service-Oriented Architectures. In (Seliger, G. et al., eds.): *Sustainable Manufacturing - Hand in Hand to Sustainability on Globe: Proceedings of the 17th Global Conference on Sustainable Manufacturing*, pp. 503–510, 2020.
- [BTN20] Binks, A.; Toniolo, A.; Nacenta, M.: *Enhancing Text Editors with Graph Visualisations*, University of St Andrews, 2020.
- [Ca19] Candido, P. H. V. et al.: Semantic Web-based System for Light Scattering Using the Generalized Lorenz-Mie Theory. In: *2019 Photonics & Electromagnetics Research Symposium - Spring (PIERS-Spring)*, pp. 3217–3224, 2019.
- [Ce21] Cesario, A. et al.: Development of a digital research assistant for the management of patients' enrollment in oncology clinical trials within a research hospital. *Journal of Personalized Medicine* 11, no. 244, 2021.
- [Ch20] Chandrashekar Murthy, B. N. et al.: Prediction of Water Demand for Domestic Purpose Using Multiple Linear Regression. In (Smys, S., Iliyasu, A.M., Bestak, R., Shi, F., eds.): *New Trends in Computational Vision and Bio-inspired Computing: Selected works presented at the ICCVBIC 2018*, pp. 811–817, 2020.
- [Ci20] Ciulla, L.: *User Research and Real User Problems: Improving the User Experience of Online Shopping*, University of Connecticut, 2020.
- [Da21] Dandabathula, G. et al.: *Design and Development of Aquayaan: An IoT based Robotic Boat for Inland Water Surveys*, 2021.
- [De20] Del Río, N. G. et al.: Health promotion for childhood obesity: An approach based on self-

- tracking of data. *Sensors* 20/13, pp. 3778, 2020.
- [Di18] Dizon, C. C. et al.: Development of an Open-Space Visual Smart Parking System. In: International Conference on Advanced Computing and Applications (ACOMP), pp. 77–82, 2018.
- [Ea19] East, A. R.: Timetable Scheduling via Genetic Algorithm, National University of Ireland, 2019.
- [EKK19] Espenakk, E.; Knalstad, M. J.; Kofod-Petersen, A.: Lazy Learned Screening for Efficient Recruitment. In (Bach, K. ed.): Case-Based Reasoning Research and Development, pp. 64–78, 2019.
- [Ga19] Garg, S.: Group Emotion Recognition, University of Manchester, 2019.
- [Gr20] Gray, F. M. et al.: Occupant Feedback and Context Awareness: On the Application of Building Information Modeling and Semantic Technologies for Improved Complaint Management in Commercial Buildings. In: 25th IEEE International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (ETFA), pp. 101–108, 2020.
- [HB19] Hobert, S.; Berens, F.: Small Talk Conversations and the Long-Term Use of Chatbots in Educational Settings—Experiences from a Field Study. In (Følstad, A. et al., eds.): Chatbot Research and Design, pp. 260–272, 2019.
- [HS20] Haghghati, A.; Sedig, K.: VARTTA: A Visual Analytics System for Making Sense of Real-Time Twitter Data. *Data* 5/1, no. 20, 2020.
- [Hu19] Huynh, S. T.: Developing App Features for Figure Drawing Practice, Worcester Polytechnic Institute, 2019.
- [HZ18] Hu, K.; Zhu, J.: A Progressive Web Application on Ancient Roman Empire Coins and Relevant Historical Figures with Graph Database. In (Ioannides, M. et al., eds.): Digital Heritage. Progress in Cultural Heritage: Documentation, Preservation, and Protection, pp. 235–241, 2018.
- [Ka20] Kavanagh, C. S.: Künstliche Intelligenz in der Kultur: Design und Entwicklung eines Chatbots für kulturfinder.sh., Kiel University of Applied Sciences, 2020.
- [Kh17] Khan, Z. et al.: Developing Knowledge-Based Citizen Participation Platform to Support Smart City Decision Making: The Smarticipate Case Study. *Information* 8/2, no. 47, 2017.
- [Ku20] Kuntke, F. et al.: Die GeoBox-Vision: Resiliente Interaktion und Kooperation in der Landwirtschaft durch dezentrale Systeme. In (Hansen, C.; Nürnberger, A.; Preim, B., eds.): Mensch und Computer 2020 - Workshopband, 2020.
- [La18] Lakatosova, P.: Taxi system front-end, Charles University, 2018.
- [Li20] LIFE LEMA Team: LIFE LEMA’s TECHNICAL SYNTHESIS REPORT. 2020.
- [LR19] Lux, M.; Rinderle-Ma, S.: Analyzing User Behavior in Search Process Models. In (Cappiello, C.; Ruiz, M., eds.): Information Systems Engineering in Responsible Information Systems, pp. 182–193, 2019.
- [LSK20] Lee, H. E.; Shin, W.; Kim, K. H.: An Assistant Service for Customers in QR-payment with the Merchant Presented Mode. In: International Conference on Information Networking (ICOIN), pp. 682–686, 2020.

-
- [Ly18] Lyndon-James, P.: Networked System and Method for Increasing Brand Awareness and Data Collection Using Gamification, U.S. Patent Pub. No. US20180060901A1, 2018.
- [Ma18] Mahi, S. M. AI: Multi-Modal Multi sensor Interaction between Human and Heterogeneous Multi-Robot System. In: Proceedings of the 20th ACM International Conference on Multimodal Interaction, pp. 524–528, 2018.
- [Ma20a] Magalhães, V. E. F.: Flexible and Interactive Navigation in Synthesized Environments, Universidade do Porto, 2020.
- [Ma20b] Markovic, M. et al.: Integrating Internet of Things, Provenance, and Blockchain to Enhance Trust in Last Mile Food Deliveries. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, no. 226, 2020.
- [MB20] Morgan, J.; Berry, G.: Systems and methods for processing content using a pattern language, U.S. Patent Pub. No. US20200143261A1, 2020.
- [Mc20] McLachlan, S. et al.: Real-time Online Probabilistic Medical Computation using Bayesian Networks. In: IEEE International Conference on Healthcare Informatics (ICHI), pp. 1–8, 2020.
- [Me19] Mendes, F. M. et al.: EJ: A Free Software Platform for Social Participation. In (Bordeleau, F. et al., eds.): *Open Source Systems*, pp. 27–37, 2019.
- [Mu20] Murciego, Á. L. et al.: Voice Assistant and Route Optimization System for Logistics Companies in Depopulated Rural Areas. *Sustainability* 12/13, no. 5377, 2019.
- [NLA19] Nayak, K. L.; Latha, A.; Akhtar, M. E.: A Survey on Data Driven Intelligent Public Transportation using LoRa. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management (IJRESM)* 2/5, pp. 533–541, 2019.
- [Ou19] Ouyang, W. et al.: ImJoy: an open-source computational platform for the deep learning era. *Nature Methods* 16/12, pp. 1199–1200, 2019.
- [Pa17] Pathak, N. et al.: Designing a Multilingual Virtual Agent Capable of Interacting with Uneducated People for Automated Data Collection. In: IEEE Symposium Series on Computational Intelligence (SSCI), pp. 1–7, 2017.
- [PNB19] Paul, U.; Nekrasov, M.; Belding, E.: EmerGence: A Delay Tolerant Web Application for Disaster Relief. In: Proceedings of the 20th International Workshop on Mobile Computing Systems and Applications, no. 167, 2019.
- [PSM20a] Prasad, R. B.; Singh, A.; Marathe, J.: Ionic4 and Pay-Pal Merging for Apps and Progressive Web Apps. *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science (IRJMETS)* 02/09, pp. 243–246, 2020.
- [PSM20b] Prasad, R. B.; Singh, A.; Marathe, J.: Ionic 4 Paypal Payment Integration for Apps and Progressive Web Apps. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)* 07/09, pp. 3234–3235, 2020.
- [Ri20] Richter, J. et al.: KOI: An Architecture and Framework for Industrial and Academic Machine Learning Applications. In (Simian, D.; Stoica, L. F., eds.): *Modelling and Development of Intelligent Systems*, pp. 113–128, 2020.
- [Rw18] Rwomushana, I. et al.: Fall armyworm: impacts and implications for Africa, 2018.

- [Sa19a] Santos-Gago, J. M. et al.: SportsWoman: A semantic-based recommender platform for women who practice sports. *Journal on Advances in Theoretical and Applied Informatics* 5, no. 1, 2019.
- [Sa19b] Santos-Gago, J. M. et al.: Towards a Personalised Recommender Platform for Sportswomen. In (Rocha, Á. et al., eds.): *New Knowledge in Information Systems and Technologies*, pp. 504–514, 2019.
- [Sa21] Samah, K. A. F. A. et al.: Genetic Algorithm Adaptation To Optimize Smartphone Recommendation System (Srcs). *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine* 08/02, pp. 78–90, 2021.
- [Sh20] Shah, A.; Abhishek, D. M.; Aneesh, R.; Aishwarya, S. R.; Taj, T.: Community web application for event management platform. *International Journal of Progressive Research in Science and Engineering (IJPRSE)* 01/05, pp. 116–120, 2020.
- [Sp19] von Sperling, O. K.: *UnB Sense : a web application to probe for signs of depression from user profiles on social media*, University of Brasília, 2019.
- [SRW20] Sukel, M.; Rudinac, S.; Worrying, M.: Detecting Urban Issues With the Object Detection Kit. In: *Proceedings of the 28th ACM International Conference on Multimedia*, pp. 4518–4520, 2020.
- [Sz19] Szemat-Vielma, W. et al.: Innovative Digital Well Construction Planning Solution Enhances Coherency and Efficiency of the Drilling Design Process. In: *Abu Dhabi International Petroleum Exhibition and Conference (ADIP)*, 2019.
- [Tu18] Tulala, P. et al.: *HUSSY . io – disrupting the oldest profession*, 2018.
- [Va20] Vazquez, A. G. et al.: Image-Guided Surgical e-Learning in the Post-COVID-19 Pandemic Era: What Is Next? *Journal of Laparoendoscopic and Advanced Surgical Techniques* 30/09, pp. 993–997, 2020.
- [VGG20] Vohra, D.; Gunjan; Gandhi, D. A.: Incentivized Techbin: a Step Towards Sustainable Environment. *International Journal of Engineering Applied Sciences and Technology (IJEAST)* 05/02, pp. 141–148, 2020.
- [Vi17] Villamayor, J. C.: *Car Features Recognition for Insurance Applications using Machine Learning*, Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha, 2017.
- [We19] Wenzel, M. et al.: New Ways of Data Entry in Doctor-Patient Encounters. In (Meinel, C.; Leifer, L., eds.): *Design Thinking Research: Looking Further: Design Thinking Beyond Solution-Fixation*, pp. 159–178, 2019.
- [Wi19] Williford, B. et al.: DrawMyPhoto: Assisting Novices in Drawing from Photographs. In: *Proceedings of the 2019 on Creativity and Cognition*, pp. 198–209, 2019.
- [YY19] Yemelyanov, A.; Yemelyanov, A.: Performance Evaluation Process and Express Decision. In (Ayaz, H., eds.): *Advances in Neuroergonomics and Cognitive Engineering*, pp. 279–287, 2019.
- [Zh20] Zhuravleva, A.: *Progressive Web Camera Application using OpenCV WebAssembly module*, Aalto University, 2020.